

INDICATORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENERGY SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN BY 2030. ROLE DIFFERENTIAL TARIFFS

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Abstract. The article provides an overview of the energy sector of the republic. Problematic issues of integration of large-scale renewable energy construction projects accepted for implementation into the energy system of the republic are considered and differentiated tariffs for electricity are applied.

Keywords: stations, power plants, natural gas.

Introduction. Currently, the installed capacity of power plants in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 17 GW, including: the capacity of JSC "Thermal Power Plants" - 14.5 GW (85% of the total capacity); JSC "Uzhydroenergy" - 2.4 GW (14.1%); stations and isolated stations - 133 MW (0.001%) (Fig.1). [1. p-5, 2].

Figure 1 Installed capacity of the Power Plants

The implementation of reforms in the power sector by 2030 is envisaged taking into account the decommissioning of physically obsolete plants (5.5 GW), the available capacity of power plants will amount to 29.3 GW, including: TPP (natural gas) - 15.1 GW (51.5%); TPP (coal) - 1.7 GW (5.8%);

HPP - 3.8 GW (12.96 %); WPP - 3 GW (10.23 %); PVPP - 5 GW (17.1 %), including 1 GW of battery energy storage system (BESS); NPP-2.4 GW (8.2%)(Fig. 2)[1. p-5, 2].

Renewable energy sources (RES). Uzbekistan is one of the countries with wide access to RES. According to studies conducted by international financial and research institutions, the country's wind energy potential is estimated between 520 GW and 1,000 GW, and solar potential up to 3,000 GW. Other renewable energy sources (RES), especially geothermal water with low enthalpy and biomass potential of 15-17 GW, having relatively low potential, can provide up to 1 GW.

Figure 2 Installed capacity variation in 2020-2030.

The country annually receives 890 thousand TWh of solar energy (theoretical potential). According to scientific studies and calculations of the International Institute of Solar Energy of Uzbekistan, the technical potential of electricity generation from solar energy is more than 3,000 TWh per year. Cloudless days are 250-270 days per year, the sun shines 2850-3050 hours per year. Utilizing 6-13% of this technical potential can meet the country's electricity needs for 2050 in the amount of 180-400 TWh (Fig. 3). [3.p.-]

Figure 3. Solar and wind energy potential versus demand in 2050.

In connection with the development of RES in Uzbekistan, legal acts have been adopted, such as the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Use of Renewable Energy Sources" dated 21 May, 2021, "On Public-Private Partnership" dated 10 May, 2019. In accordance with the establishment of the legal framework and procedures for the implementation of projects in the field of RES development [4, 5], Figures 3 and 4 show maps of solar radiation and wind speed in the regions of the country.

Figure 4. Map of solar radiation in Uzbekistan.

Figure 5. Wind speed map of Uzbekistan.

According to the approved target parameters, by 2030, the share of electricity generated from renewable energy sources will be increased to 25 percent. For this purpose, plants with a total capacity of about 10 GW will be commissioned (including 5 GW of solar photovoltaic plants, 3 GW of wind power plants and 1.9 GW of hydropower plants). [6]

RES integration issues into the energy system. At the present stage of development, the energy system of Uzbekistan is faced with the problems of deficit of electricity generation. This deficit is mainly caused by the shortage of own natural gas production, as well as generating base and maneuvering capacities of power plants. In turn, this has caused in recent years a number of systemic accidents covering the entire Unified Energy System of Central Asian countries due to overloading of powerful power plants and a number of inter-system transmission lines. Thus, there is a clear opportunity to eliminate the deficit, either through imports of electricity and natural gas or through large-scale integration of renewable energy sources. In both cases, the integration of

energy storage (ES) into the energy system is of paramount importance. Note that since 2023, under the contract with the Russian Federation, natural gas is supplied through the Gazli-Ural gas pipeline in reverse mode. [7.p-733, 8]

The active and mass introduction of RES, mainly RES and PVPP, due to the non-permanent or variable specifics of operation of these generation sources, raises many questions and challenges to ensure smooth integration of these sources into the power system. In this regard, special attention is paid to finding solutions to this problem by forecasting their active capacity and studying their impact on the efficiency of the power system.

The integration of large PVPP and wind power plants (WPP) into the energy system planned for 2030 did not imply the presence of storage facilities. As it is known, the integration of RES within 3-4% of the total capacity of the energy system will not have a noticeable impact on its dynamic properties. With further increase of RES share in the power balance of the power system, the problems of reliability and stability of modes increase. Therefore, it is important to ensure controllability of regimes and stability of parallel operation of RES with the power system when integrating large volumes of RES by using BESS. The first steps in this direction have been taken - for example, together with the Chinese company Gezhouba, an energy storage system with a capacity of 150 MW will be created in 2024. According to the data of Wood Mackenzie Consulting Company on the deployment of energy storage systems in the world and the forecast of market development until 2024, the global market of energy storage systems by 2024 will grow 13 times, and the volume of the market of RE in physical terms (cumulative total) will grow from 12 GWh to 158 GWh. [9,10]

Electricity tariffs. Within the framework of the 2030 Vision, work is underway to implement several large investment projects, it is necessary to dismantle obsolete and outdated electrical equipment and commission new units. All these activities require capital expenditures, which should be covered by selling electricity at a unit tariff, defined as the ratio of gross revenue requirement (GRR) to the estimated production volume. In this case, the GRR is made up of:

$$GRR = TAOE + AAC + RIC$$

Where:

TAOE - total annual operating expenses,

AAC - annual amortization charges,

RIC - return on invested capital.

Meanwhile, social protection of the population is one of the priority areas of Uzbekistan's state policy, designed to make electricity affordable and accessible to low-income households by introducing targeted social assistance measures to compensate eligible consumers for increased electricity costs, such as tariff scales defining different tariffs depending on the level of consumption. Currently, electricity tariffs for households are 450 sums (~3.6 cents) for use up to 200 kWh per month, 900 sums for volume exceeding this norm.

Large-scale introduction of RES into the energy system can lead to uncontrolled generation. Energy generated by PVPP can lead to surplus electricity during daytime hours and deficit during evening peak hours. Thus, regulating the daily load schedule requires the involvement of consumers in regulating the load schedule. An effective way is to introduce differentiated tariffs: higher tariffs for peak load hours (evening maximum) and lower tariffs for excess load hours.

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